

THE IMPORTANCE OF NEW INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Nasirova is the daughter of Gulnoza Fakhriddin

I graduated from UzDJTU in 2021.

From September 2021, an English teacher at Beshbola max 51 school, Jomboy district, Samarkand region

ABSTRACT The article talks about the importance of using new pedagogical technologies in the teaching of English, and all the possibilities of the student are analyzed, taking into account the complexity of mastering the subject. Also, examples of new methods in language development are given and its importance is revealed.

Key words: English language, methodology, science, method, lesson, student, pedagogue

"President's prize will be established for schools with high performance in foreign languages" - Shavkat Mirziyoyev. In fact, it is the task of us pedagogues to create school lessons and textbooks that can meet the standards of countries recognized by the world through the development of a foreign language. It is good that the students who can speak English are found in the first grade of the school. Especially, the number of students achieving international degrees in a foreign language is increasing day by day. Besides our national university, we are also pleased that more than seven out of one student is a student in the world's top 1000 universities. By the way, mastering science is a somewhat complicated process. Mastering a foreign language like one's own language depends on the skill of the pedagogue. The use of new pedagogical methods is also important and effective. Compared to the traditional lesson, the student's mastery rate is higher in the lesson

conducted using new technologies. Below, we will talk about the essence of such new pedagogical methods and their effects in practice. -survey", "Modeling", "Creative work", "Problematic education" are noted. According to the data, the interactive educational strategies include "Brainstorming", "Boomerang", "Gallery", "Zig-zag", "Zinamazina", "Muzyorar", "Rotastia", "Snowball". When distinguishing interactive educational strategies from the composition of interactive educational methods, the approach to organizing group work is based on the fact that, in a certain sense, it is compared to strategic planning. In fact, these strategies are more related to interactive educational methods, and there are no other differences between them. Interactive graphic organizers: "Fish skeleton", "BBB", "Conceptual table", "Venn diagram", "T-table", "Insert", "Cluster", "Why?", "How?" and b. The separation of interactive graphic organizers is based on the fact that the main ideas in such classes are expressed in written form in various graphic forms. In fact, working with these graphic organizers is more related to interactive educational methods. Let's analyze some of the new mininteractive methods below. This method ensures students' activity in the training process, encourages them to think freely and frees them from the inertia of the same thinking, collects various ideas on a specific topic, it also serves to learn to overcome the thoughts that appeared at the initial stage of the process of solving creative tasks.

Pedagogical technology is essentially organized with the help of forms, methods and tools, increases the effectiveness of pedagogical activity and determines mutual cooperation between teachers. In addition, it ensures students' acquisition of thorough knowledge of educational subjects. forms independent, free and creative thinking skills in students. At the same time, necessary conditions are created for students to realize their potential. It is also necessary to guarantee the priority of democratic and humanitarian ideas in the pedagogical process.

REFERENCES

1. Jalolov Jamal. Foreign language teaching methodology. "Teacher" publishing house, Tashkent - 2012.
2. Bekmuratova U. B. Abstract on "Using innovative technologies in teaching English". Tashkent - 2012
3. Kholdorova M., Fayziyeva N., Rikhsittilayeva F. "USE OF HELPING TOOLS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE". Tashkent: TDPU named after Nizomi, 2005